

**MSMES AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS IN INDIA:
EXPLORING EMERGING INTERSECTIONS AND POLICY
IMPLICATIONS**

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Abstract

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) play a central role in the Indian economy by creating multidimensional economic structures. Recent studies have highlighted the significant contribution of MSMEs to achieving India's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The present study examines the intersection of MSMEs and the SDGs to explore underdeveloped themes in the Indian context. The study employs a qualitative, descriptive and conceptual research design based on secondary sources, including government reports, policy documents, and scholarly literature. The paper analyses the interrelationship between MSMEs and selected SDGs through four major intersecting themes, namely affordable and clean energy, reduced inequalities, climate action, and global partnerships. The findings indicate that MSMEs contribute beyond economic productivity by supporting clean energy initiatives, regional balance, rural livelihoods, sustainable production practices, environmentally adaptive development, international cooperation and institutional partnerships. For effective policymaking, the study highlights the need for Sustainable Finance and Green Transition, Inclusive Entrepreneurship and Regional Development, Green Products and Institutional Support and Global Partnerships and Market Integration.

Keywords: MSMEs; Sustainable Development Goals; Policy; SDGs; Enterprises, India

1. Introduction:

1.1 Background and Context:

One of the most important policy issues of the twenty-first century is sustainable development, especially for developing nations seeking to balance social justice, economic expansion, and environmental sustainability. In this regard, the United Nations' 2015 adoption

of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) provides a comprehensive global framework for inclusive and sustainable development. Strengthening decentralised economic structures, employment-oriented production systems, and locally embedded entrepreneurship are necessary for a developing nation like India to achieve these objectives. Within this broader developmental framework, Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) occupy a crucial position due to their significant contribution to industrial production, employment generation, exports, and regional development.

Over the past 50 years, the Indian economy's MSME sector has grown into a highly active and dynamic sector. By encouraging entrepreneurship and creating numerous job possibilities at relatively lower capital costs—second only to agriculture—it makes a substantial contribution to the nation's economic and social development. MSMEs are ancillary units that supplement larger companies, and this sector makes a substantial contribution to the nation's inclusive industrial development. In order to satisfy the needs of both domestic and international markets, MSMEs are expanding their reach across many economic sectors and creating a wide variety of goods and services (Ministry of MSME, Annual Report 2022-23)

1.2. Review of Literature:

1.2.1 MSMEs in the Indian Economy:

MSMEs play an important role in strengthening local economies, reducing regional disparities, and facilitating balanced economic development across rural and urban areas. These enterprises are essential to India's economy, as they significantly boost regional growth, employment, and industrial output. They are looped into the rural economy, as the majority of MSMEs operate in rural India (Vasal, 2020). MSMEs include a wide range of industries, including manufacturing, services, and trade, and are defined by investment and turnover restrictions. There are almost 63 million MSMEs in India as of March 2024, many of which are registered through the Udyam Registration Portal (Ministry of MSME, 2024). According to the Centre for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS), as reported by Rossow (2022), small business strategies are a crucial component of most nations' industrial policies because they can create jobs. According to Indian government estimates, there are about 60 million MSMEs, which together employ 111 million people, or about 25% of the country's total workforce.

MSMEs account for 40% of India's exports and 28% of the country's GDP (6.11% of manufacturing GDP and 24.63% of service GDP). Among these groups, "micro" businesses (turnover of less than 600,000 USD) make up approximately 95 per cent of the market (Ministry of MSME, 2018). MSMEs contribute 90% of enterprises, 80% of the non-agriculture labour force, 6.11% of manufacturing GDP, 24% of service sector GDP, 33.4% of manufacturing activities, and 45% of total exports (Prakash et al., 2021). The Khadi and Village Industries Commission, the Coir Board, the National Small Industries Corporation, the National Institute for Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises, and the Mahatma Gandhi Institute for Rural Industrialisation are all under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises. By providing access to government programs and policies, these groups play a critical role in helping MSMEs. According to predictions, the number of MSMEs in India is expected to rise from 63 million to roughly 75 million, rising at a compound annual growth rate of 2.5 per cent (Ministry of MSME, 2024).

1.2.2 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs):

Adopted by the United Nations in 2015 as part of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, a comprehensive framework for sustainable and inclusive development was introduced. The SDGs provided a new framework for addressing economic, social, and environmental concerns. The 17 interconnected goals emphasise poverty reduction, gender equality, clean and affordable energy, decent work, sustainable industrialisation, responsible consumption, and climate action, all of which are highly relevant to developing economies like India (Ferrata, 2019). Two major subject clusters emerged in a research study through trend analysis: environmental and economic factors, which highlight sustainability and climate change, and health and human welfare, which highlight gender concerns and public health. Strong connections between SDG 8, SDG 12, and SDG 13 have been found in India's SDG research, suggesting that these objectives are at the centre of the nation's SDG research agenda (Raman et al., 2025).

1.2.3 Relation Between MSMEs and SDGs:

MSMEs directly contribute to 9 of the 17 UN SDGs. MSMEs create jobs at low capital cost, thereby signifying the potential to end hunger and poverty (Pedersena, 2018). Therefore, MSMEs are considered key drivers of employment and entrepreneurship for young and adult populations across all social sectors, and they employ a disproportionate number of women, thus ensuring “gender equality” and “reduced inequalities”. MSMEs implement “decent work and economic growth” and “industry innovation and infrastructure” as they help achieve higher levels of economic productivity with technological upgrading and innovation. MSMEs mostly consider sustainable business practices because they are more flexible than larger companies, thereby achieving “responsible consumption and production” (Gupta, 2025). The contribution of MSMEs toward SDGs extends beyond economic productivity and enters the broader domain of sustainable and inclusive development. Due to their decentralised structure, labour-intensive nature, and local economic embeddedness, MSMEs possess significant potential to contribute toward poverty reduction, employment generation, women entrepreneurship, regional development, and environmentally adaptive production systems. (Verma, 2019)

The majority of the publications highlight how MSMEs contribute to the economy by creating jobs, expanding industries, and fostering entrepreneurship. The role of MSMEs in inclusive development, green transition, and sustainable production systems has been emphasised in more recent studies. However, research on the relationship between MSMEs and goal-specific sustainability outcomes remains limited, especially in the Indian context. Therefore, by examining new connections between MSMEs and specific SDGs, the current study aims to go beyond descriptive economic analysis.

1.3 Research Gap:

Although several studies have examined the role of MSMEs in employment generation, entrepreneurship, and industrial development, limited scholarly attention has been given to understanding MSMEs as multidimensional contributors to achieving specific SDGs to build a sustainable India. Existing studies focus either on economic productivity or policy interventions. The interrelationship between MSMEs and goal-specific sustainability is comparatively underexplored. The present study seeks to address this gap by examining the

emerging intersections between MSMEs and selected SDGs within the Indian context.

1.4 Methodology:

The present study employs a qualitative, descriptive, and conceptual research design using secondary data sources. To critically analyse the emerging intersections between MSMEs and the SDGs in the Indian context, a conceptual approach was adopted, with interpretative and thematic analysis rather than empirical measurement. The study relies on government reports, policy documents, MSME annual reports, peer-reviewed journal articles, and publications on development studies, sustainability, and entrepreneurship. The selection of sources was based on their relevance to MSMEs, the sustainability discourse, the SDGs, and Indian policy frameworks. Thematic and content analysis techniques were employed to identify recurring developmental themes and major intersecting domains between MSMEs and selected SDGs. The study's findings are restricted to interpretive analysis rather than empirical generalisation because it is conceptual in character and depends on secondary sources.

1.5 Objectives:

- To examine the role of MSMEs in contributing to Sustainable Development Goals in India.
- To find relevant intersecting themes among MSMEs and SDGs.
- To explore policy measures and future directions needed to strengthen the existing efforts and initiatives.

2. Intersecting Themes: MSMEs and SDGs in India:

MSMEs are involved in varied sectors that help achieve many objectives under different goals. MSMEs perform multidimensional developmental functions through employment generation, entrepreneurship promotion, industrial decentralisation, and sustainable production practices. Several studies have indicated that MSMEs play a direct role in achieving SDGs related to No Poverty, Zero Hunger, Gender Equality, Decent Work and Economic Growth, Industry Innovation and Infrastructure, Reduced Inequalities, and Responsible Consumption and Production (Raman, 2025; Pedersena, 2018; Verma, 2019; & Ministry of MSME, 2021)

Contextualising MSMEs in the framework of SDGs is the core idea of this study. In this paper, the focus has been on the intersecting theme between MSMEs and the SDGs. Several SDGs, which were not found to be primarily relevant to or to intersect with MSMEs in previous research, have been found to resonate in the present study. The synergy between MSMEs and the SDGs was highly relevant across four domains. Table 1 presents the four major intersecting domains between MSMEs and SDGs. The study has identified the intersecting themes of MSMEs with Goals 7, 10, 13, and 17 out of the total 17 Sustainable Development Goals. These intersections offer fresh analytical perspectives on MSMEs' multifaceted contributions to India's sustainable development.

Table 1: Intersecting Themes between MSMEs and SDGs

SDGs	MSMEs Contribution	Key Developmental Outcome
SDG 7	Renewable energy adoption	Clean energy transition
SDG 10	Rural entrepreneurship	Reduced inequalities
SDG 13	Green products and the coir industry	Climate adaptation
SDG 17	International cooperation	Global partnerships

2.1 MSMEs and SDG 7: Affordable and Clean Energy:

According to reports by the Institute for Sustainable Development and International Relations (IDDRI, 2015) and the Sustainable Development Solutions Network (SDSN), it is important to build a domestic industry for low-carbon technologies. Domestic markets are vital for technological innovation, learning, and domain-specific adaptations. Clean energy supply and demand-side technologies will have a huge market to launch a global-scale domestic industry in India. The domestic industry can partner with global technology and carbon finance businesses. Clean energy technologies have successfully replaced fossil fuels in MSMEs by promoting biomass thermal gasifiers (Sinha, 2015). MSMEs can implement clean energy solutions through sustainable finance (SF) initiatives such as green bonds and climate funds (Ranjan et al., 2022). With an emphasis on energy efficiency in MSMEs, the CEFI Roadmap seeks to remove financial and investment barriers in India's clean energy sector (OECD, 2022). Financial, technological, and regulatory factors are of utmost significance in India as MSMEs in the automotive sector adapt to the goal of electric mobility (Dash, 2023). MSMEs are increasingly integrating low-carbon technologies and renewable energy systems, indicating their growing contribution to India's shift toward sustainable industrial development.

2.2 MSMEs and SDG 10: Reduced Inequalities:

MSMEs contribute significantly to reducing socio-economic and regional inequalities in India through their widespread presence across rural and urban areas, labour-intensive production systems, and a decentralised entrepreneurial structure. The distribution of MSME enterprises demonstrates their substantial role in promoting inclusive economic participation beyond metropolitan and industrially advanced regions. According to the MSME Annual Report (2020–21), out of the estimated 633.88 lakh MSME enterprises in India, around 324.88 lakh enterprises (51 per cent) are located in rural areas, while 309 lakh enterprises (49 per cent) operate in urban areas (Ministry of MSME, 2021). With roughly 497.78 lakh job opportunities in rural areas and 612.10 lakh in urban areas, the sector also creates a large number of employment opportunities in both regions. This distribution illustrates MSMEs' ability to promote equitable regional development and reduce economic opportunity gaps. Additionally, the prevalence of microenterprises—more than 630 lakh units—indicates that entrepreneurship is accessible to small-scale and economically disadvantaged producers, who often remain outside the formal industrial sector. MSMEs support inclusive growth and directly contribute to SDG 10, which emphasises reducing inequality within and among societies by facilitating the creation of local jobs, encouraging small-scale entrepreneurship, and enabling marginalised populations to participate in productive economic activities. Studies that highlight MSMEs' contributions to employment creation, rural industrialisation,

and inclusive economic growth in developing economies have also highlighted their importance in fostering equitable development (Prakash et al., 2021; Ministry of MSME, 2021).

2.3 MSMEs and SDG 13: Climate Action:

According to UNDP, Climate action is defined as "stepping up efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and strengthen resilience and adaptive capacity to climate-induced impacts, including: improving education, awareness-raising, and human and institutional capacity with respect to climate change mitigation, adaptation, impact reduction, and early warning; integrating climate change measures into national policies, strategies, and planning; and addressing climate-related hazards in all countries." The coir industry provides employment to more than 7.30 lakh persons and has contributed significantly to increasing exports over the years. Use of coir has increased due to its environmentally friendly nature. There is significant potential for value addition in coir products through technological interventions and diversification into coir geotextiles (Ministry of Micro and Small Enterprises, Achievement Report 2014-18). The sustainable nature of the coir industry demonstrates the potential of MSMEs in supporting climate adaptation and environmentally responsible production practices. MSMEs can support climate adaptation through resource-efficient production methods, waste-reduction techniques, energy-efficient technologies, and sustainable manufacturing practices, in addition to more conventional eco-friendly businesses. India's long-term climate resilience and low-carbon development ambitions can be greatly aided by bolstering environmentally adapted MSMEs.

2.4 MSMEs and SDG 17: Partnerships for the Goals:

To foster cooperation among MSMEs, the Government of India enters into long-term agreements, or Memorandums of Understanding (MoUs), with several nations. These collaborations cover a wide range of topics, including capacity building, industrial surveys and feasibility studies, enterprise-to-enterprise collaboration, participation in exhibitions and trade shows, exchanging business missions, technology transfer, etc. In order to improve international cooperation and the global integration of Indian MSMEs, the Ministry of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises has launched a number of programs. To foster collaboration in areas such as enterprise collaboration, technology transfer, skill development, industrial training, export promotion, and market access, the Ministry has signed numerous long-term agreements, Memorandums of Understanding (MoUs), and Joint Action Plans with various nations. Bilateral engagements with countries across Asia, Africa, Europe, and the Middle East, along with international workshops, conventions, and business forums, have facilitated institutional networking and global business interaction for Indian MSMEs. Additionally, the growing role of MSMEs in international development cooperation and capacity-building is reflected in initiatives carried out by the National Small Industries Corporation (NSIC), such as cooperation agreements and the establishment of vocational training and incubation centres in several African countries under the India Africa Forum Summit (IAFS) (Ministry of MSME, Achievement Report 2014-18). These programs demonstrate the growing importance of international integration and institutional alliances in building Indian MSMEs' potential for innovation and long-term competitiveness.

Figure 1: Intersecting Themes between MSMEs and Sustainable Development Goals in India

Figure 1: Intersecting Themes between MSMEs and SDGs in India

Despite MSMEs' increasing contribution to sustainable development in India, as shown in Figure 1, several institutional and structural obstacles continue to limit their capacity for sustainable change. Organisational hurdles, financial barriers, policy and regulatory restrictions, and technology limitations are among the most important. These issues are interrelated, necessitating coordinated policy responses rather than discrete actions. MSMEs sometimes prioritise short-term financial rewards over ecologically friendly practices because they lack the required sustainability standards (Nautiyal et al., 2026). In order to assist the green and inclusive transformation of India's MSME sector, the report emphasises the necessity of integrated institutional support, improved regulatory processes, technological accessibility, and sustainability-oriented policy frameworks.

3. Policy Implications and Way Forward:

MSMEs have significant potential to support sustainable development through job creation, decentralised industrialisation, clean energy initiatives, sustainable production methods, and global economic participation. However, a more integrated policy strategy that links economic growth to social and environmental sustainability is needed to increase MSMEs' role in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals.

3.1 Sustainable Finance and Green Transition:

One of the major policy implications emerging from the study is the need to enhance access to sustainable finance for MSMEs, particularly for enterprises adopting renewable energy technologies, environmentally adaptive production systems, and green innovations. Financial incentives, low-interest credit facilities, and climate-oriented investment support can strengthen MSMEs' transition toward sustainable industrial practices.

3.2 Inclusive Entrepreneurship and Regional Development:

To reduce regional disparities and advance balanced economic growth, the report also emphasises the importance of strengthening rural and semi-urban MSMEs. The competitiveness and sustainability of MSMEs operating in economically backward locations can be enhanced by greater government emphasis on infrastructure development, digital inclusion, skill development, and market accessibility. Targeted assistance for socially disadvantaged entrepreneurial groups and women-led businesses can also improve inclusive economic participation and help eradicate socioeconomic gaps.

3.3 Green Products and Institutional Support:

Stronger institutional support mechanisms for green products, technological upgrading, and energy-efficient production systems are also necessary to address the growing interaction between MSMEs and the transition to a low-carbon economy. Public-private partnerships, research partnerships, and capacity-building initiatives can help MSMEs adopt environmentally friendly products. In this regard, legislative measures that emphasise AI-enabled market systems, resource efficiency, digital sustainability, circular economy practices, and ESG-oriented business frameworks might better integrate MSME development with the broader sustainability agenda.

3.4 Global Partnerships and Market Integration:

The study also emphasises the importance of international cooperation and institutional partnerships in enhancing the capacity of Indian MSMEs to compete globally. Cooperative platforms for knowledge transfer, export promotion, innovation exchange, and sustainable business development can boost the long-term resilience of the

MSME sector in a rapidly evolving global economy.

The convergence of sustainability-oriented policies with entrepreneurship development and localised economic planning will determine the future course of MSMEs in India. The contribution of MSMEs to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals in India can be greatly increased by bolstering institutional coordination, sustainable finance mechanisms, technological flexibility, and inclusive policy frameworks. The future competitiveness and sustainability of MSMEs in India may be further shaped by the increasing significance of digital sustainability, AI-enabled market systems, and ESG-oriented business frameworks.

4. Conclusion:

The present study highlights the multidimensional contributions of MSMEs to the SDGs in the Indian context. With a labour-intensive character, a decentralised industrial structure, and localised production systems, MSMEs have become significant drivers of inclusive and sustainable development, in addition to their contributions to economic growth and job creation. The study found strong connections between MSMEs and several Sustainable Development Goals, especially in global collaboration, affordable and clean energy, reduced inequality, and climate action. These connections show that MSMEs support broader social and environmental change alongside economic productivity. The results also show that MSMEs have significant potential to support environmentally adapted economic activities, sustainable production methods, rural livelihoods, and balanced regional development. Their widespread presence across rural and semi-urban regions makes them important institutional

actors in reducing developmental disparities and strengthening grassroots entrepreneurship in India. The study further reveals that, to increase MSMEs' long-term contribution to sustainable development in India, sustainable finance, technological modernisation, institutional coordination, regional development, and supportive regulatory frameworks remain crucial. The study contributes to the existing literature by identifying emerging intersections between MSMEs and selected Sustainable Development Goals from an Indian policy perspective.

The present study is conceptual in nature and primarily based on secondary sources. Future research may focus on empirical assessments of MSME-led sustainable practices, sector-specific case studies, and comparative analyses across regions to better understand the evolving relationship between MSMEs and the Sustainable Development Goals in India.

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